

Robust Cooperative Sparse Representation Solutions for Detecting and Mitigating Spoofing Attacks in Autonomous Vehicles

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Abstract—The new era of Industry 4.0 and its key-enabling Internet of Things technologies promises fundamental advances during data collection, processing and analysis from a variety of agents and sensors, for the collective benefit of society. In this regard, connected and autonomous vehicles equipped with integrated perception sensors and communication abilities formulate a cluster or swarm of intelligent nodes capable to transform the transportation sector into a new smart mobility system. However, its feasible operation may be potentially threatened by hijackers whose goal is to cause malfunctioning to critical vehicular sensors, harnessing the perception system of vehicle. Therefore, in this paper we discuss the impact of cyberattacks such as GPS spoofing on autonomous vehicles, and design efficient detection and mitigation centralized schemes which provide location awareness and security monitoring over the whole cluster of vehicles. More specifically, we exploit the cooperation among the interacting vehicles, and develop robust sparse coding solutions based on graph signal processing and Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers. Cooperative based approach is further benefited by a in-vehicle module which provides spoofing detection alerts at the level of individual vehicle. Experimental analysis using the renowned CARLA simulator indicates highly efficient mitigation performance for different rates of compromised vehicles, as well as spoofing detection metrics greater than 94%.

Index Terms—GPS spoofing, autonomous vehicles, Graph Signal Processing, ADMM, sparse coding

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent Transportation Systems and its main pillar of connected and autonomous vehicles (CAVs) feature many promising advantages in order to integrate smart mobility as a core aspect of modern societies. Reduced traffic accidents, less traffic congestion, optimized route planning, among other benefits, are indicative of the potential of autonomous driving technologies. However, at the era of Internet of Things and big data, multisensory CAVs are vulnerable to cyberattacks which target explicitly data processing and analysis layer in order to knock-out their perception systems [1]. To be more specific, adversarial attacks [2] compromise the camera

based perception of vehicle, by misclassifying nearby objects. Furthermore, GPS jamming or spoofing [3] aims to either block the signals to be transmitted to satellites or produce a false though realistic GPS based position. Both cases exhibit a critical threat to autonomous driving localization ability, with severe consequences in feasible and reliable operation of vehicles. In this work, we will mitigate and detect spoofing attacks against CAVs, by exploiting the collaboration among them. Our goal is to "clean" GPS from spoofing outliers utilizing robust graph signal processing tools, in order to establish accurate and reliable location monitoring of swarm of CAVs in a centralized manner.

The threat that GPS spoofing poses against autonomous vehicles is mainly due to its effective implementation in realistic conditions [4]. For example, techniques that aim either to fool an estimation algorithm (Kalman filter) with outliers in order to corrupt its output [5] or even manipulate the trajectory of an unmanned aerial vehicle towards an arbitrary destination unnoticed [6], are already present in literature. Mitigating spoofing outliers relying on robust statistic estimators such as Huber, M and MM, and the non-linear least squares principle that is used for GPS positioning is discussed in [7]. The authors of [8] exploit a similar approach where M-estimator is employed in order to mitigate GPS outliers that don't follow Gaussian distribution. Sensor faults, not just GPS, detection and isolation via unscented Kalman Filter is presented in [9], by assessing the correlation between data that is generated within the same sensor. A tightly coupled approach of inertial navigation system and GPS using weighted least-squares and Kalman filter is described in [10], so as to detect GPS spoofing attacks against an aircraft.

However, the potential of cooperation, and more specifically of cooperative localization of CAVs [11] in order to remove the impact of spoofing without compromising the estimation accuracy, remains rather unnoticed. To the best of our knowledge, this work presents a novel robust approach based on CAV's cooperation for simultaneous secured location estimation as well as spoofing detection. The general idea of the proposed mechanism has been presented in [12], though CVX optimization framework had been employed. On the contrary, in this work we derive a convex mini-

The work of N.P., A.S.L., and C.A. has been supported by EU's H2020 research programm TRUSTEE (ID: 101070214). The work of S.Z.N.Z., C.L., and M.K.M has been supported by the EU's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE) and from the Government of the Republic of Cyprus through the Directorate General for European Programmes, Coordination and Development.

mization algorithm based on Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) [13] so as to perform effective and secure location awareness by an overall fusion center. Furthermore, the defense mechanism is assisted by detection labels of potentially spoofed vehicles, which are provided by an in-vehicle module. Robust sparse coding is achieved by integrating to the target cost function the l_1 norm of GPS's outliers, assuming that only a subset of swarm's vehicles may be compromised. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We derive an ADMM based robust and cooperative algorithm, capable of mitigating the biases of GPS caused by spoofing and additionally identify which vehicles are compromised with detection accuracy greater than 94% in an unsupervised manner and under the investigated conditions.
- Reliable and secure location monitoring over the swarm is benefited by indicative alerts of spoofing generated by in-vehicle localization approach, achieving performance equal to that if GPS was operating in normal mode.
- Experimental setup and evaluation study has been conducted in CARLA autonomous driving simulator [14], indicating very promising results in tackling GPS spoofing against different rates of attacked vehicles.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II is dedicated to preliminaries; Section III describes the proposed cooperative defense mechanism; Section IV presents the simulation and numerical results, while Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This Section will introduce the system model of the problem at hand, as well as the in-vehicle module deployed on individual vehicles which provides a rough location estimation and indicative alerts about spoofing.

A. Cooperative Measurement Modelling

CAVs of a swarm are multisensory systems or agents, which exploit advanced data fusion and processing approaches along with V2V communication so as to enhance their perception ability and effectively perform challenging driving actions. Equipped sensors including cameras, LIDAR, sonars, GPS, inertial measurement unit (IMU), etc., are responsible for identifying nearby objects of interest i.e., cars or pedestrians (example shown in Fig. 1). Perception of autonomous vehicles is usually described by relative and self measurement models. For instance, considering that vehicle i at time instant t is moving at the 2D plane (similar for 3D space), its ground truth location is given by $\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} = [x_i^{(t)} \ y_i^{(t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Additionally, useful metrics for analysing the surrounding environment include relative distance $z_{d,ij}^{(t)}$ and azimuth angle $z_{az,ij}^{(t)}$ with respect to nearby vehicle j : $z_{d,ij}^{(t)} = \|\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} - \mathbf{x}_j^{(t)}\|$ and $z_{az,ij}^{(t)} = \text{atan2}(y_j^{(t)} - y_i^{(t)}, x_j^{(t)} - x_i^{(t)})$, respectively. Due to sensor measurement noise, which can be modelled by the Gaussian distribution

(a) 3D point cloud from LIDAR (b) CAVs establish connections, formulating swarms in the form of a graph topology

Fig. 1. Nearby objects (red) in the LIDAR plane of ego vehicle (green) and example of swarm of CAVs.

$\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$, we end up with self and relative measurement models describing the perception system of vehicle i :

- Self measurement model about position:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{n}_p^{(t)}, \quad \mathbf{n}_p^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_p^{(t)}) \quad (1)$$

- Relative measurement models:

$$\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} = z_{d,ij}^{(t)} + n_{d,ij}^{(t)}, \quad n_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_d^{(t)}) \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)} = z_{az,ij}^{(t)} + n_{az,ij}^{(t)}, \quad n_{az,ij}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{az}^{(t)}) \quad (3)$$

However, the positioning outliers or biases added to GPS are highly random and not expected to follow any probabilistic distribution. That is because in practise the attacker aims either to block or degrade the GPS signals between the satellites and the receivers. Thus, the outlier $\mathbf{o}_i^{(t)} = [\mathbf{o}_i^{(x,t)} \ \mathbf{o}_i^{(y,t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ added to position measurement is chosen from the uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}[\alpha, \beta]$. The new measurement model of spoofed position is given by:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{p,i}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}_i^{(t)} + \mathbf{n}_p^{(t)} + \mathbf{o}_i^{(t)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{n}_p^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_p^{(t)}), \quad \mathbf{o}_i^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{U}[\alpha, \beta]$$

Furthermore, in order to take advantage of the inherent geometry of swarm's topology, we extend relative measurements (2) and (3), by utilizing the so-called differential coordinates [15]. As such, we define for vehicle i the 2D vector $\delta_i^{(t)} = [\delta_i^{(x,t)} \ \delta_i^{(y,t)}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ as the barycenter of its neighborhood $\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}$. The latter contains the neighboring vehicles to i within a range r_c . Therefore, we have that: $\delta_i^{(x,t)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} (x_i^{(t)} - x_j^{(t)})$ and $\delta_i^{(y,t)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} (y_i^{(t)} - y_j^{(t)})$. However, $(x_i^{(t)} - x_j^{(t)}) = -z_{d,ij}^{(t)} \cos z_{az,ij}^{(t)}$ and $(y_i^{(t)} - y_j^{(t)}) = -z_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin z_{az,ij}^{(t)}$. In practice, the relative measurement models of (2) and (3) are used, and as a matter of fact we end up with the definition of differential coordinates of vehicle i :

$$\delta_i^{(x,t)} \approx \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} \left(-\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} \cos \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\delta_i^{(y,t)} \approx \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}|} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{(t)}} \left(-\tilde{z}_{d,ij}^{(t)} \sin \tilde{z}_{az,ij}^{(t)} \right) \quad (6)$$

In the following, we will show how the connectivity topology of swarm and the associated self and relative measurements can be utilized by an overall fusion center (used e.g. at a public authority) for reliable, accurate and safe location monitoring of vehicles.

B. In-Vehicle Measurement Modeling

Besides location-dependent measurements from neighboring vehicles, the CAV can achieve self-location awareness by utilizing two additional sources of information, i.e., *absolute* location using GPS-free measurements from the surrounding wireless network infrastructure and *relative* location based on the previously estimated CAV location and data from in-vehicle inertial sensors. For instance, the CAV may carry a device based on Software-Defined Radio (SDR) technology that receives ambient signals of opportunity such as radio signals from surrounding wireless infrastructure (e.g. cellular, Wi-Fi, DVB-T, etc.) and collects timing, angle, or signal strength measurements from the corresponding transmitters. Assuming that the locations of the transmitters are known in advance, a Localization Algorithm (LA) estimates the current location of the CAV based on the available measurements, i.e., *absolute* location, independently from the GPS readings; an overview of such LAs is available in [16]. In this case, the device outputs the estimated location of the CAV $\mathbf{x}_{L,i}^{(t)} = [x_{L,i}^{(t)}, y_{L,i}^{(t)}]^\top$ modeled as a Gaussian random variable $\mathbf{x}_{L,i}^{(t)} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_i^{(t)}, \Sigma_{L,i}^{(t)})$, where $\Sigma_{L,i}^{(t)} = \text{diag}_2(\sigma_{L,i}^{(t)})$ is the covariance matrix of the CAV's locations estimated by the LA with standard deviation $\sigma_{L,i}^{(t)}$ in both coordinates. As described in [17], these absolute locations can be refined by means of Bayesian filtering, e.g., Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) and in-vehicle multi-source data fusion. In particular, in the *Prediction* phase the CAV's location is projected ahead in time using the previous location of the CAV and inertial sensor readings (e.g., accelerometer, gyroscope, steering angle, etc.) and a mobility model of the CAV e.g., bicycle model. The CAV's predicted location, i.e., *relative* location, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)} = [\hat{x}_i^{(t+1)}, \hat{y}_i^{(t+1)}]^\top$ at time instance $t+1$ follows a Gaussian distribution, i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)} \sim \mathcal{N}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)}, \Sigma_{\hat{\mathbf{x}},i}^{(t+1)})$, where $\Sigma_{\hat{\mathbf{x}},i}^{(t+1)}$ is the covariance matrix that denotes the uncertainty of the predicted location. Next, in the *Update* phase, the EKF algorithm fuses the CAV's predicted location $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)}$ with the estimated absolute location $\mathbf{x}_{L,i}^{(t+1)}$ provided by the LA. The output is the refined location estimate $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)}$ that is assumed to be drawn from a Gaussian distribution, i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)} \sim \mathcal{N}(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_i^{(t+1)}, \Sigma_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}},i}^{(t+1)})$, where $\Sigma_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}},i}^{(t+1)}$ is the covariance matrix of the refined location computed implicitly by the EKF algorithm.

III. ROBUST CENTRALIZED LAPLACIAN BASED LOCALIZATION AND SPOOFING DETECTION

In this Section, we will derive and present the proposed robust and cooperative sparse coding algorithm based on Graph Laplacian Processing (a well known graph signal processing tool [15]) and ADMM, a simple but powerful convex optimization algorithm which is well suited for l_1

norm problems but also when the target variables of cost function are separable.

A. Outliers' mitigation and detection via sparse coding

Assuming that the swarm of Fig. 1-(a) contains N CAVs, fusion center can formulate the degree $\mathbf{D}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ and adjacency $\mathbf{A}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ matrices of swarm's graph, based on the data transmitted by vehicles. Matrices $\mathbf{D}^{(t)}$ and $\mathbf{A}^{(t)}$ represent the V2V connections among vehicles. Additionally, we define graph Laplacian matrix of the swarm as $\mathbf{L}^{(t)} = \mathbf{D}^{(t)} - \mathbf{A}^{(t)}$. We collect to matrix $\Delta^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$ the differential coordinates, to matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_p^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$ the (spoofed or not) noisy positions of vehicles and to matrix $\mathbf{B}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N \times 2}$ the concatenated differential coordinates and noisy positions, i.e., $\mathbf{B}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \Delta^{(t)} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_p^{(t)} \end{bmatrix}$. Moreover, we extend matrix $\mathbf{L}^{(t)}$ with the identity matrix \mathbb{I}_N , i.e., $\tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}^{(t)} \\ \mathbb{I}_N \end{bmatrix}$. Thus, the 2D positions of vehicles of the swarm described by matrix $\mathbf{X}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$ can be estimated by [18]:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{(t)}}{\text{argmin}} \left\| \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \mathbf{X}^{(t)} - \mathbf{B}^{(t)} \right\|^2 \quad (7)$$

Solution of (7) derives from linear least-squares minimization, i.e., $\mathbf{X}^{(t)} = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)T} \right)^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)T} \mathbf{B}^{(t)}$. However, in the case where some vehicles have been compromised, the impact of spoofing deteriorates the accuracy of location estimation. As such, in [12] a reformulation of (7) is proposed in order to remove the biases of spoofing from noisy positions measurements, by introducing the outliers matrix $\mathbf{O}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{(t)}, \mathbf{O}^{(t)}}{\text{argmin}} \left\| \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \mathbf{X}^{(t)} - (\mathbf{B}^{(t)} - \mathbf{O}^{(t)}) \right\|^2 + \left\| P_\Omega(\mathbf{O}^{(t)}) \right\|_1 \quad (8)$$

The l_1 norm imposes the sparsity of outliers' matrix since we assume that due to limited capabilities of a hijacker only a subset of swarm's vehicles may be attacked ($\sim 5\%$ - 20%), while operator $P_\Omega(\cdot)$ selects the second half of $\mathbf{O}^{(t)}$ as it corresponds to spoofed positions and sets the first one equal to zero. Operator $P_\Omega(\cdot)$ can also be derived by the detection alerts of in-vehicle module. To be more specific, instead of addressing all the noisy position measurements as potentially spoofed, we exploit the in-vehicle module in order to identify the most probable spoofed positions, setting all the others equal to zero. This choice positively affects the performance of the proposed mechanism, as it will be shown in the numerical results. Therefore, by solving (8), fusion center mitigates the impact of spoofing, "cleans" and turns GPS into a trusted sensor, and realizes safe and secured location monitoring of swarm.

B. Alternating direction method of multipliers

Target cost function (8) of sparse coding was minimized in [12] using CVX software. However, in real applications specific algorithmic steps should be derived in order to have a feasible solution. ADMM algorithm [13] can be used to minimize (8), ensuring the convergence towards the solution. That is due to the separability of target variables

and appropriateness for l_1 norm minimization. Initially, we form the augmented Lagrangian by introducing dual variable $\mathbf{Y}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$:

$$\mathcal{L} = \left\| P_{\Omega} \left(\mathbf{O}^{(t)} \right) \right\|_1 + \mathbf{Y}^{(t)T} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \mathbf{X}^{(t)} - (\mathbf{B}^{(t)} - \mathbf{O}^{(t)}) \right) + \frac{\rho}{2} \left\| \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \mathbf{X}^{(t)} - (\mathbf{B}^{(t)} - \mathbf{O}^{(t)}) \right\|^2 \quad (9)$$

Through appropriate modifications and replacing $(1/\rho) \cdot \mathbf{Y}^{(t)}$ with $\mathbf{U}^{(t)}$, we end up with:

$$\mathcal{L} = \left\| P_{\Omega} \left(\mathbf{O}^{(t)} \right) \right\|_1 + \frac{\rho}{2} \left\| \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \mathbf{X}^{(t)} - (\mathbf{B}^{(t)} - \mathbf{O}^{(t)}) + \mathbf{U}^{(t)} \right\|^2 \quad (10)$$

In order to estimate the target variables, we have to perform alternating minimization for each one of the variables keeping the others fixed for K iterations. Therefore, minimizing (10) with respect to $\mathbf{X}^{(t)}, \mathbf{O}^{(t)}, \mathbf{U}^{(t)}$, we have that:

$$\mathbf{X}^{(k+1,t)} := \left(\tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)T} \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \right)^{-1} \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)T} \left(\mathbf{B}^{(t)} - \mathbf{O}^{(k,t)} - \mathbf{U}^{(k,t)} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$P_{\Omega} \left(\mathbf{O}^{(k+1,t)} \right) := P_{\Omega} \left(S_{1/\rho} \left(\mathbf{B}^{(t)} - \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)T} \mathbf{X}^{(k+1,t)} + \mathbf{U}^{(k,t)} \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{U}^{(k+1,t)} := \mathbf{U}^{(k,t)} + \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \mathbf{X}^{(k+1,t)} - \mathbf{B}^{(t)} + \mathbf{O}^{(k+1,t)} \quad (13)$$

Soft thresholding operator $S_{\kappa}(x) = (1 - \kappa/|x|)_+ x$ ensures the sparsity of outliers matrix. Steps (11)-(13) summarize the ADMM-based proposed robust sparse coding algorithm.

C. In-Vehicle Spoofing Detection

The in-vehicle spoofing detection mechanism is based on the intuition that the GPS location measurement $\tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(t)}$ given by (4) will deviate significantly from the refined location estimate $\tilde{x}_i^{(t)}$ in case of spoofing attack. Therefore, a threshold can be properly selected to signify a spoofing attack in case it is violated. To formalize this, the in-vehicle attack detection indicator function at time t is given by:

$$I^{(t)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \left\| \tilde{z}_{p,i}^{(t)} - \tilde{x}_i^{(t)} \right\| > T_d \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (14)$$

where T_d is a user-defined detection threshold. $I^{(t)} = 1$ indicates that an attack is detected, while $I^{(t)} = 0$ indicates that everything is normal. The threshold T_d can be selected empirically by assuming an initial attack-free time period where the CAV is moving on the road network and collects GPS location measurements, while computing the GPS-free refined location estimates by processing the in-vehicle sensory data with the EKF algorithm. Calculating the euclidean distance among all location pairs provides the Empirical Cumulative Distribution Function (ECDF) of the deviations and the threshold can be selected at a user-defined percentile value as described in [17].

D. Robust Centralized Spoofing Detection

Apart from robust location monitoring, it is of major importance the fusion center of public authority to be aware of potentially attacked vehicles in order to publish appropriate alerts. For this task, we measure the l_2 norm (or euclidean

distance) between the estimated positions and the, spoofed or not, noisy positions from GPS. Distances below a threshold e.g., equal to $10m$, are set to zero. Afterwards, we employ 2-means clustering on those distances and define two groups of information. The largest centroid between the two groups indicates the group of ids of compromised vehicles. The main steps of the proposed sparse coding algorithm named **Robust Centralized Laplacian based Localization (RCLL)** are summarized in **Algorithm 1**. The conceptual architecture of the proposed methodology is shown in Fig. 2.

Algorithm 1: RCLL

Input: Number of iterations $K, \rho, \Delta^{(t)}, \tilde{\mathbf{Z}}_p^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}, \tilde{\mathbf{L}}^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2N \times 2}$, spoofing detection labels
Output: $\mathbf{X}^{(K,t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2}$, ids of compromised vehicles

- 1 **for** $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ **do**
- 2 Each CAV extract its noisy (spoofed or not) position from GPS and differential coordinates using their visual sensors;
- 3 Each CAV runs the in-vehicle localization module;
- 4 CAVs transmit to fusion center the appropriate information (relative measurements, noisy positions and spoofing detection labels);
- 5 Selection operator $P_{\Omega}(\cdot)$ is defined using the detection labels of in-vehicle module;
- 6 Fusion center formulates the Laplacian matrix;
- 7 **for** $k = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
- 8 Do steps (11)-(13);
- 9 **end**
- 10 Fusion center identifies compromised vehicles using 2-means clustering;
- 11 **end**

Fig. 2. Conceptual architecture of robust cooperative sparse coding.

To sum up, this Section has presented the details of the proposed sparse coding approach. Initially, we formulated the least-squares based Centralized Laplacian based Localization, which fits for location awareness and monitoring tasks when noisy positions are not affected by spoofing. As such, and in order to address positioning outliers, we have extended the previous framework to its robust version utilizing the sparsity constraints of l_1 norm and derived the three main iterative steps of ADMM algorithm. Finally, a simple yet effective approach for identifying compromised vehicles is also discussed, based on 2-means clustering. As a last remark, although centralized implementation introduces additional

communication and computational costs for its deployment, they are a prerequisite for secured location monitoring over swarms of CAVs in urban environments which are under the threat of hijackers.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Experimental setup

CARLA simulator has been used in order to extract the realistic trajectories of 60 vehicles, for $T = 1000$ time instances and time interval $dt = 0.05$ sec. We choose a random ego vehicle (trajectory shown in Fig. 4-(b)) and formulate the corresponding swarm of connected vehicles assuming that connectivity links are established within a range of 30m. Spoofing trajectories are generated by adding outliers drawn from $\mathcal{U}[5, 40]$, and target ego vehicle along with a subset of swarm's vehicles. This rate of attacked vehicles (r.a.v.) was set equal to 5%, 10%, 15% and 30% of swarm's size. The main points of the evaluation study considered the convergence properties of our scheme, the location awareness accuracy with the presence of GPS outliers, and finally how efficiently we identify compromised (or not) vehicles. To simulate measurement noise, we set $\Sigma_p^{(t)} = \text{diag}(4m, 3m)$, $\sigma_d = 2m$ and $\sigma_{az} = 6^\circ$. Moreover, number of iterations $K = 40$ and $\rho = 0.01$. Regarding the localization metrics, we used the root mean square location awareness and localization error over time horizon ($RLAET$ and $RLET$) [19], in order to measure the location estimation accuracy of the whole swarm as well as ego vehicle, respectively. Finally, we measured the average number of true positives, false positives, true negatives and false negatives (aTP, aFP, aTN, aFN), as well as average accuracy, i.e., $aACC = (aTP + aTN)/(aTP + aFP + aTN + aFN)$, so as to assess the detection performance of our algorithm.

B. Evaluation study

1) *Convergence of ADMM*: Initially, we present the convergence curves of **RCLL** with and without the detection labels from in-vehicle approach, i.e., **RCLL(+)** and **RCLL(-)** respectively, in Fig. IV-B1 for different rates of attacked vehicles. Fig. IV-B1 demonstrates the averaged location awareness error ($ALAE$) of the swarm over the required number of iterations. As it can be seen, **RCLL(+)** reduces $ALAE$ from 14m, 30m, 44m and 90m, respectively, to almost 5m at the end of the iterative procedure. However, the convergence speed deteriorates as the rate increases, highlighting the fact that spoofing mitigation is more challenging when the number of attacked vehicles is larger. More specifically, $ALAE$ at 10-th iteration is equal to 6m, 7m, 10m and 20m for rates equal to 5%, 10%, 15% and 30%. On the contrary, **RCLL(-)** actually increases $ALAE$ after the 10-th iteration or stabilizes to high enough value (Fig. IV-B1(d)), and as such we have to employ this scheme for much fewer number of iterations and correspondingly with much less location estimation accuracy. Therefore, it is deduced that the a-priori knowledge of compromised vehicles using the in-vehicle approach has a significant impact on improving the

location awareness accuracy during the iterations of **RCLL** scheme.

Fig. 3. Convergence with and without indicative detection labels from in-vehicle block.

2) *Location awareness accuracy*: The reliable location awareness monitoring is also demonstrated in TABLE IV-B2, which summarizes $RLAET$ and $RLET$ metrics. **RCLL(+)** is capable not only to remove the biases from (sp)oofted GPS, but to achieve even greater performance than the theoretically intact and (n)ormal GPS sensor. It also performs much more accurate than in-vehicle module, due to the benefits of cooperative measurements fusion. For example, with $r.a.v. = 15\%$ we achieved $RLAET$ equal to 2.33m, with respect to 5m and 12.76m of normal and spoofed GPS. As $r.a.v.$ increases, so does the $RLAET$ of **RCLL(+)** and spoofed GPS, since greater amount of vehicles have been compromised. In all four cases, it is apparent that the proposed robust scheme achieves more than 50% and 80% improvement in location estimation accuracy than normal and spoofed GPS. This fact emphasizes the benefits of robust sparse coding in mitigating GPS outliers in an effective manner. Furthermore, **RCLL(-)** performs more worse than its counterpart, as it was noted also in the previous subsection, and especially for the case of $r.a.v. = 30\%$ its accuracy exceeds that of normal GPS. Probabilistic interpretation of **RCLL(+)**'s superior accuracy in terms of individual localization error of ego vehicle is provided in Fig. 4-(a), where we see that it outperforms all the other solutions. For example, with probabilities between 82% and 98% the error of **RCLL(+)** ranges between $\sim 3m$ and $\sim 4m$, significantly lower than the other approaches.

3) *Performance of spoofing detection*: To assess the spoofing detection performance, we summarized in TABLE IV-B the corresponding classification metrics with **RCLL(+)**, **RCLL(-)** and in-vehicle module, assuming that *positive* and *negative* correspond to spoofed and non-spoofed vehicle. The last column of this table contains the average accuracy which describes the rate of predictions made correct

TABLE I
METRICS OF DETECTION PERFORMANCE WITH RCLL(+), RCLL(-) AND IN-VEHICLE MODULE

<i>r.a.v.</i>	<i>aTP</i>	<i>aFP</i>	<i>aTN</i>	<i>aFN</i>	<i>aACC</i>
5%	0.05 / 0.04 / 0.05	0.01 / 0.02 / 0.12	0.93 / 0.92 / 0.82	0.003 / 0.002 / 0.001	0.98 / 0.97 / 0.88
10%	0.08 / 0.07 / 0.08	0.01 / 0.02 / 0.12	0.9 / 0.89 / 0.79	0.005 / 0.006 / 0.001	0.98 / 0.97 / 0.88
15%	0.1 / 0.1 / 0.11	0.01 / 0.02 / 0.11	0.87 / 0.86 / 0.77	0.009 / 0.01 / 0.002	0.96 / 0.96 / 0.88
30%	0.16 / 0.15 / 0.18	0.01 / 0.02 / 0.11	0.80 / 0.78 / 0.7	0.01 / 0.02 / 0.003	0.96 / 0.94 / 0.88

TABLE II
RESULTS OF *RLAET* (*m*) AND *RLET* (*m*) WITH DIFFERENT METHODS

<i>r.a.v.</i>	RCLL(+)	RCLL(-)	<i>in-vehicle</i>	<i>n. GPS</i>	<i>sp. GPS</i>
5%	2.29 / 2.16	2.92 / 2.77	5.3 / 5.17	5 / 4.97	9.48 / 25.38
10%	2.33 / 2.17	3.16 / 2.96	5.3 / 5.17	5 / 4.97	11.44 / 25.58
15%	2.45 / 2.19	3.98 / 3.20	5.3 / 5.17	5 / 5.1	12.76 / 24.71
30%	2.76 / 2.49	5.12 / 5	5.3 / 5.17	4.99 / 4.94	15.72 / 24.73

Fig. 4. CDF of individual localization error of ego vehicle with *r.a.v.* = 15% and trajectory of ego vehicle in CARLA map.

using the different approaches. In-vehicle module's *aACC* is equal to 88% regardless of *r.a.v.*, while both unsupervised **RCLL(+)** and **RCLL(-)** achieved *aACC* larger than 94%. Even without the detection labels **RCLL(-)** performed very efficiently in identifying correctly the compromised (or not) vehicles. **RCLL(+)** was once again more effective, since the increased location estimation accuracy positively affected the detection performance, even though *aACC* reduces as *r.a.v.* increases. Thus, we conclude that robust sparse coding offers increased location estimation accuracy but also identifies in a very effective and unsupervised manner the spoofed vehicles exploiting both the benefits of cooperation among vehicles as well as the properties of l_1 norm modelling.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has contributed towards designing a novel robust cooperative sparse coding approach for reliable location awareness and identification of spoofed CAVs of a swarm. Based on Graph Laplacian processing and l_1 norm modelling of positioning outliers, we derived an ADMM based solution which is further assisted by indicative spoofing detection labels provided by the in-vehicle localization approach. The complementarity of cooperative measurement fusion and in-vehicle module has demonstrated its benefits in CARLA simulator based experiments regarding the convergence speed of ADMM, overall location awareness accuracy, and highly efficient detection of compromised vehicles.

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